

SHORT NOTES

Synthesis of 3',4'-Dimethoxy- and 3',4'-Dimethoxy-6-methyl-flavan-4- β -ols and 6-Methylflavan-4- α -ol

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Flavans containing a 4-hydroxyl group are of increasing importance because of growing interest in the study of flavan-3,4-diols (leucoanthocyanidins). Reduction of 4-oxoflavans, catalytically or otherwise with lithium aluminium hydride, has been closely studied and much attention has been directed to the configuration and conformation of the 4-hydroxyl group thus produced^{1,2}. These 4-hydroxyflavans are termed as 4- β -ols and have been shown to be 2,4-*cis* compounds³⁻⁴. Similarly, the 4- α -epimers have been prepared by the action of nitrous acid on 4-aminoflavans⁵ and very recently by the lead tetra-acetate oxidation of the corresponding flavans^{6,7}; these have been assigned the 2,4-*trans* configuration^{7,8,10}.

These compounds have been synthesised to study the reactivity of the 4-hydroxyl group in the two epimers (α and β).

3',4'-Dimethoxyflavan-4- β -ol.—3',4'-Dimethoxyflavan-4-one was prepared by cyclisation of the corresponding chalcone with ethanol and 36.V-H₂SO₄. The flavanone (2.5 g.) and boric acid (0.6 g.) were dissolved in rectified spirit (200 ml.). Sodium borohydride (0.8 g.) was then added cautiously in small lots. A white solid separated within 10 minutes. The mixture was kept at the room temperature for 3 hr. with occasional shaking. The solvent was distilled and the residue was dissolved in water. The clear solution was acidified with very dilute acetic acid when a white solid was obtained. It was recrystallised from methanol in colorless light needles, m.p. 153°, yield 80%. (Found: C, 71.3; H, 6.4. C₁₇H₁₆O₄ requires C, 71.4; H, 6.3%).

3',4'-Dimethoxy-4-acetoxyflavan.—3',4'-Dimethoxyflavan-4- β -ol (0.5 g.) was dissolved in dry pyridine (5 ml) and acetic anhydride (5 ml) was added to this; the mixture

1. Bognar and Rakosi, *Acta Chim. Acad. Sci. Hung.*, 1957, 13, 217.
2. Kashikar and Kulkarni, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1958, 1084.
3. Lewis *et al.*, *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 20.
4. Lillya *et al.*, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1963, 783.
5. Bognar and Rakosi, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1959, No. 19, p. 4.
6. Bokadia *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 3308.
7. Verma and Bokadia, *Ourr. Sci.*, 1964, 21, 648.
8. Lillya *et al.*, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1963, 84.

mixture was kept overnight. Finally it was warmed for 15 min. on a water bath and poured on an excess of ice water. On keeping the diluted mixture overnight in a refrigerator, a white crystalline solid separated. It was recrystallised from methanol, m.p. 113°. (Found: C, 69.3; H, 6.1. $C_{19}H_{20}O_3$ requires C, 69.5; H, 6.1%).

6-Methyl-3',4'-dimethoxyflavan-4- β -ol.— $LiAlH_4$ (0.42 g.) was kept well cooled in dry ether (150 ml). 6-Methyl-3',4'-dimethoxyflavan-4-one⁹ (2.5 g.) was added to this in small lots. The mixture was refluxed on a water bath for 2 hr. (The reaction was carried out under perfectly dry conditions using a calcium chloride guard tube). The reaction mixture was decomposed by adding water; the organic layer was separated and dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate. Removal of the solvent yielded a white solid which was recrystallised from methanol in colorless, light needles, m.p. 142°. yield 80%. (Found: C, 71.8; H, 6.8. $C_{18}H_{20}O_4$ requires C, 72.0; H, 6.6%).

6-Methyl-3',4'-dimethoxy-4-acetoxyflavan was prepared by the method described above. Recrystallisation from methanol afforded shining needles, m.p. 141°. (Found: C, 70.3; H, 6.5. $C_{20}H_{22}O_5$ requires C, 70.1; H, 6.4%).

6-Methylflavan-4- α -ol.—6-Methylflavan was prepared by Clemmensen reduction of 6-methylflavan-4-one¹⁰. 6-Methylflavan (3 g.) and lead tetra-acetate (5 g.), dissolved in benzene (120 ml), were refluxed for 12 hr. till a negative test for tetravalent lead was obtained. The reaction mixture was filtered and the precipitate was washed with benzene. The filtrate was washed with water and dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate. Removal of the solvent provided a yellowish gum which was dissolved in methanol (50 ml) and refluxed with KOH (5 g.) for 2 hr. The product was worked up in the usual manner and it was distilled under vacuum, yielding a pale yellow liquid, b.p. 86-87°/4-5 mm, yield 40%. (Found: C, 80.4; H, 6.7. $C_{16}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 80.0; H, 6.6%).

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9. Verma and Bokadia, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1965, 3, 565.

10. Verma and Bokadia, *this issue*, p. 91.